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Gender differences in management and outcome of patients with acute myocardial infarction

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on behalf of the PRIAMHO II Investigators · Show all authors

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Abstract

Background

The study objectives were to assess any gender differences in the application of diagnostic and therapeutic procedures and their impact on outcome in patients with acute myocardial infarction (AMI).

Methods

Prospective cohort study of patients in the PRIAMHO II registry. 58 randomly selected public hospitals in Spain included 6209 patients with AMI admitted to Coronary/Critical Care Unit from May 15 to December 15 2000 with 1-year follow-up. Data were gathered on use of coronary angiography and reperfusion procedures, on a combined outcome variable (including death, reinfarction, postinfarction angina, and stroke during hospital stay), and on 28-day and 1-year mortality rates.

Results

4641 (74.75%) of the patients were male and 1568 (25.5%) female. No gender differences in coronary angiography or reperfusion therapy use were found. However, female sex alongside age, use of reperfusion therapy, diabetes mellitus, previous revascularization, previous AMI, and higher Killip class were predictors of the combined outcome variable, with an adjusted OR of 1.21 (CI 95% 1.02–1.42).

Conclusions

No association was observed between the gender of patients with AMI and the application of diagnostic or therapeutic procedures. Nevertheless, female sex behaved as an independent adverse short-term prognostic factor.